

Control synthesis of iron nanoparticle and iron/graphene nanocomposites

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Abstract

Metal nanoparticles show distinct physical, chemical properties from their bulk counterparts due to higher surface to volume ratio and play major roles in various applications such as optical, electrical, thermal etc. Additionally, Graphene has been one of the most investigated 2D materials in last decade due to their excellent electronic, optical and chemical properties. Therefore in the present work to study the metal nanoparticle/graphene nanocomposite, we have investigated the optical properties of iron nanoparticles and their composite with graphene. In this work, we have demonstrated successful synthesis of Iron nanoparticles (dimensions ~ 10-15 nm) by room temperature chemical synthesis route. Further, reduced graphene was synthesized by reduction of graphite oxide and iron nanoparticles were decorated on its surface by chemical route to form iron/graphene nanocomposite. Synthesized samples were characterized using XRD, SEM and FTIR spectroscopy etc. Optical properties of synthesized samples were studied using UV-visible absorption spectroscopy.

Keywords: Fe Nanoparticles, Graphene, optical properties.

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